

21NRM05 STASIS

D5: Report on the translation of *in vitro* safety testing results to realistic exposure conditions considering combined GC and RF induced heating

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Glossary

MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MR	Magnetic Resonance
RF	Radiofrequency
SAR	Specific Absorption Rate
DBS	Deep Brain Stimulator
IPG	Implantable Pulse Generator
AIMD	Active Implantable Medical Device
CP	Circular Polarization
GC	Gradient Coil
RMS	Root Mean Square
TSM	Tissue Simulating Medium

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1 Summary

In this deliverable, gradient-induced heating concepts and procedures proposed in ISO/TS 10974 are extended to passive orthopedic implants and fixation devices. A Tier 2 approach is developed to reduce the overestimation of the safety limits in case of anisotropic implants, and to define testing procedures more relevant to the actual clinical conditions at which such implants are scanned. The roles of gradient and RF as implant heating sources are investigated *in silico*; recommendations for combining results of RF and gradient testing are provided in view of standardized procedures. The result is a robust methodology to streamline the *in vitro* evaluation of bulky passive implants and translate into actual clinical MRI exposures with suitable confidence levels, which is proposed in Deliverable 7 “Standard Test Method for Measurement of Gradient Magnetic Field Induced Heating On or Near Non-active Implants During Magnetic Resonance Imaging” of the STASIS project as a draft ASTM test standard.

Key outcomes of the work described in this deliverable report include:

- demonstration of significant superposition of RF and gradient heating of bulky passive implants under clinically relevant conditions
 - 65% in phantom, 10% *in vivo* worst conditions and 0.35K in realistic condition
- refined RF E-field metrics developed with lower overestimation than Tier 2
- validated representative confidence interval of *in silico* RF and gradient heating assessments

These outcomes are summarized in this report, and most are also published in the following open-access peer-reviewed scientific journal articles:

- Zanovello Umberto, Fuss Carina, Arduino Alessandro, Bottauscio Oriano. Efficient prediction of MRI gradient-induced heating for guiding safety testing of conductive implants. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine* 2023, doi:10.1002/mrm.29787
- Zanovello Umberto, Arduino Alessandro, Fuss Carina, Goren Tolga, , Bottauscio Oriano, Impact of simultaneous exposure to RF and gradient electromagnetic fields on implant MR safety labeling. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine* 2025, doi:10.1002/mrm.70059
- Arduino Alessandro, Bottauscio Oriano, Grappein Denise, Scialó Stefano, Vicini Fabio, Zanovello Umberto, Zilberti Luca, 3D–1D modelling of cranial mesh heating induced by low or medium frequency magnetic fields, *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine* 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2025.109009

2 Motivation

The heating of implants during an MR examination due to the radiofrequency (RF) field and the gradient field are potentially additive¹², yet the two phenomena are typically assessed independently; their superposition is rarely considered in safety assessments, as it is not directly required in any standard or regulatory guidance.

There are several reasons for this:

1. RF fields deposit energy directly in the biological tissues surrounding the implant, whereas gradient-induced fields deposit energy in the metallic implant. The spatial distributions of the resulting temperature increases, as well as the hotspot locations around a given implant, are significantly different.
2. GC heating is usually stronger when the implant is relatively far from the isocenter, whereas RF heating is often stronger when the implant is close to the isocenter or to the end-ring of the RF coil;
3. MR sequences which are the worst-case for GC-heating are also not typically the worst-case for RF-heating, and vice versa;
4. The test equipment of benchtop heating assessment, as well as the selected MR protocols for heating assessments in clinical scanners and the standards specifying the test protocols, are different and independently developed, encouraging their independent treatment. These methods are necessarily summarized down to heating rates, worst-case temperatures, or thermal doses of local hotspots, for implants under unrelated test exposure scenarios. Therefore, no information about the 3D spatial/temporal distributions of heat is typically available;
5. The MR sequence parameters which can limit RF-heating (SAR, B1+rms), GC-heating (dB/dt rms), or both (scan duration), are independently specified, thus RF-GC heating superposition can be mitigated by adjusting any of three parameters, creating difficulties for developing guidance.

These reasons can be subdivided into risk-based considerations (items 1–3) and practical considerations (4–5). The increasing use of high-fidelity numerical modeling of patient exposures using human body models and implant surrogates, in lieu of or in supplement to phantom-based physical testing, is relevant to several of these points. The most significant practical consideration, item 4, is surmounted by access to the full 3D spatial distribution of local hotspots granted by numerical methods, increasing the feasibility of efficiently assessing combined RF-GC heating. Numerical methods now allow potential safety risks to be reliably identified ahead of time through multi-physics in vivo simulations, rather than waiting for a clinical report of an injury directly attributed to the phenomenon in question.

Under these circumstances, the question is whether the (now feasible) effort of considering combined RF-GC heating is justified by real potential risks, *i.e.*, considering points 1–3, do realistic MR examinations produce simultaneous RF and GC heating which superposes

¹ Arduino Alessandro, Zanovello Umberto, Hand Jeff, et al. Heating of hip joint implants in MRI: The combined effect of RF and switched-gradient fields. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2021;85(6):3447

² Clementi Valeria, Zanovello Umberto, Arduino Alessandro, et al. Classification Scheme of Heating Risk during MRI Scans on Patients with Orthopaedic Prostheses, *Diagnostics*. 2022;12(8):1873.

sufficiently at the worst-case locations to justify their consideration in implant safety labeling? The first objective of this report is to identify general conditions under which the heating of GC and RF can be considered as independent or interacting, causing highest-heating scenarios. The entire analysis is performed *in silico*, simulating the exposure of anatomical human models modified by inserting the implant through virtual surgery. For the situations where superposition is found to be significant, recommendations for combining results of RF and GC testing were provided in view of standardized procedures.

The second goal of this report is to define a robust methodology to streamline the *in vitro* evaluation of bulky passive implants, to translate *in vitro* analysis into clinical MRI exposure and to provide suitable confidence levels. The analysis will include development of reference approaches for RF heating estimation of bulky passive implant, bridging the gap between ISO 10974 Tier 2 and Tier 3-type approaches to RF heating estimation; analysis of the presence of perfusion in RF and GC heating; possibility to define optimal phantom thermal properties for GC heating to match *in vivo* results; possibility to combine tests performed on single implant components to get the final behavior of the entire implant for GC heating.

The results represent a justification to streamline the *in vitro* evaluation of bulky passive implants and translate into actual clinical MRI exposures with suitable confidence levels, as well as the validated tools and metrics required to do so; this approach is proposed in Deliverable 7 “Standard Test Method for Measurement of Gradient Magnetic Field Induced Heating On or Near Non-active Implants During Magnetic Resonance Imaging” submitted to ASTM F04.15 as a standard draft item.

3 Activity A3.3.1

INRIM, ITIS and MRC will define a set of realistic exposure scenarios for performing the analysis of superposition of RF and GC heating. The considered scenarios will include different passive and active implants (at least two bulky orthopaedic implants, two orthopaedic plates, one active implant), a selection of MRI sequences (at least two classes), two hardware configurations (RF coil and GC), implant positions within the scanner (at least six positions).

The following implants were used:

- Hip implant: Implant manufactured by Adler Ortho SpA, Italy (model APTA-FIX + FIXA Ti-Por) with CoCrMo sphere, Ti+HA stem, Ti6Al4V cup and UHMW-PE liner (Figure 1a).
- Knee implant: Implant manufactured by Adler Ortho SpA, Italy (model GENUS MB) with CoCrMo femoral and tibial components and UHMW-PE liner (Figure 1b).
- Shoulder implant: Implant manufactured by LimaCorporate SpA, Italy (model TRAUMA SMR Anatomic) made in Ti6Al4V alloy (Figure 1c).
- Cranial plate: Implant manufactured by Medartis AG, Switzerland (model M2-7093S) made in titanium (ASTM F67), semi-rigid. The plate is 100mm × 100mm and 0.6mm thick (Figure 1d).
- Ankle plate: Implant manufactured by Medartis AG, Switzerland (model 4954 25S (left)) made in titanium (ASTM F136), alloy. Together with the ankle plate, two

titanium (ASTM F136) screws are considered (models 5901 50 and 5800 60) (Figure 1e).

- Active implant: The SAIMD-U implant manufactured by ITIS is considered. SAIMD-U is a verification and validation device for evaluations according to ISO/TS 10974 (Figure 2).

The electric and thermal properties of the material composing the passive above implants are listed in Table 1; the materials of the SAIMD-U are given in Annex U of that standard.

Table 1: Material electric and thermal properties

Material	El. Cond. (MSm ⁻¹)	El. Rel. Perm.	Th. Cond. (Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Sp. Heat Cap. (Jkg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Mass Dens. kg/m ³
Titanium	0.58	-	7.2	520	4420
CoCrMo	1.16	-	14	450	8445
UHMW-PE	0	2.3	0.41	1840	930

(a) Adler Ortho SpA hip Implant CAD

(b) Adler Ortho SpA knee implant CAD

(c) LimaCorporate SpA shoulder implant CAD

Figure 1: CAD models of the implants

Figure 2: ZMT SAIMD-U AIMD verification device

The following MRI sequences were considered along the next project activities:

- Echo-planar imaging (EPI): Selected to stress the heating effects due to switched gradient fields (Figure 3)
- Balanced steady-state (TrueFISP): Selected to stress both the heating due to radiofrequency and to switched gradient fields (Figure 4)
- Turbo Spin Echo (TSE): Selected to stress the heating due to radiofrequency fields (Figure 5)

As required by the protocol, six imaging positions were analyzed:

- Femur
- Knee
- Pelvis
- Abdomen
- Thorax
- Head

For each imaging position multiple implant positions were simulated according to a fixed 7cm spatial step along the z-axis (see Figure 6).

Finally, a three-axial actively shielded gradient coil with whole-body access manufactured by Nanjing Cichen Medical Technology Co., Ltd, Nanjing, China (model: Solaris-R) were used for the analyses of switched gradient field heating. 16-leg high-pass birdcage body coils were used to investigate the effects of radiofrequency heating both at 1.5T and 3T.

Figure 3: Echo-planar imaging (EPI)

TrueFisp

Figure 4: Balanced steady-state (TrueFISP)

TSE

Figure 5: Turbo Spin Echo (TSE)

Figure 6: Implant extreme positions accounted for in simulations. Between these positions, the implants have been simulated with 7cm spatial steps

4 Activity A3.3.2

ITIS with the support of INRIM will develop at least 5 realistic digital models of the body carrying the implants selected in A3.3.1. Gender, age, and BMI were considered in the selection of the body models. This activity will provide input to A3.3.3 and A3.3.4.

With reference to the implants proposed in A3.3.1, the human models implanted with the hip, knee and shoulder implants have been selected among those already prepared in the context of a previous EMPIR project (MIMAS 17IND01). In this case, it was possible to interact with the implant manufacturers to obtain implant models that fitted the human models' specific anatomy. The virtual surgery was carried out under supervision of orthopaedic surgeons.

In addition, IT'IS Foundation prepared three new models carrying an ankle plate, a cranial plate and an implantable pulse generators (IPG). The latter was obtained by properly positioning the digital model of the SAIMD-U device removing all the components except for the IPG case. Indeed, only the IPG case affects gradient-induced heating and RF-induced heating were analyzed with the ISO/TS 10974 Tier 3 approach that doesn't account for the implant digital model.

All the implants have been implanted in the Glenn human model with the only exception of the shoulder implant which has been implanted in the YoonSun model. The Glenn model is

an 84 years old man with a BMI equal to 20.54kgm⁻². The Glenn model has been selected since it is representative of the elderly population most likely do carry an orthopaedic implant. Due to difficulties in identifying a shoulder implant that fitted the Glenn's anatomy, the YoonSun human model (26 years old female with a BMI equal to 23.6kgm⁻²) has been used for this implant. Thus, the implants were:

- Glenn with the hip implant from MIMAS
- Glenn with the knee implant from MIMAS
- YoonSun with the shoulder implant from MIMAS
- Glenn and YoonSun with a Medartis M2-7093S, 100x100mm, "Mesh 3", 0.6mm thickness cranial plate
 - Plate is deformed/projected onto skulls while preserving size and shape
- Glenn and YoonSun with Medartis A-4954.25S 040989 ankle plate, each on left and right side
 - With corresponding A-5800.60 007245 (longer) and A-5901.50 042889 (shorter) screws
- Glenn and YoonSun with SAIMD-U [3] generic active implantable device (ZMT Zurich MedTech AG)
- IPG model provided with generic pacemaker, deep-brain stimulator and spinal-cord stimulator routings

A detail of each prepared model is shown in Figures 7-10.

Figure 7: Digital models of the human body carrying the hip, knee and shoulder implants.

Figure 8: Digital models of the human body carrying the SAIMD-U IPG, the cranial plate and the ankle plate.

Figure 9: Representative placement of skull mesh and ankle implants, in ViP Model YoonSun

Figure 10: Representative placement of generic active implant routings, in ViP Model YoonSun

5 Activity A3.3.3

ITIS will perform in silico RF simulations for the exposure scenarios identified in A3.3.1, using the digital models developed in A3.3.2.

As inputs from previous activities, human models from the ViP with implants implanted using virtual surgery or placement of the implant at the accurate position are already available. Implants that could be implanted on both sides of the body were always only considered on one side.

The relevant positions of the model in the birdcage were identified for each implant, corresponding to the maximum heating cases with the implant at the center or edge of the RF-coil for the imaging landmark; the step size between landmarks was 7 cm (Table 2). The position reference is labeled in the same way as the IT'IS MRlxViP database (and Annex

P of ISO 10974 IS1 draft), i.e. 0 mm represents the landmark where the RF coil isocenter is between the eyes and between the ears. The x and y positions of the models within the coils were the same as MRiXViP (and Annex P of ISO 10974 IS1 draft).

Table 2: Positions considered for each model and implant with respect to the MRiXViP position reference.

Model	Implant	Positions (from MRiXViP position reference in mm)
Glenn	knee	800, 870, 940, 1010, 1080, 1150, 1220, 1290
	hip	380, 450, 520, 590, 660, 730, 800, 870, 940, 1010, 1080, 1150
	ankle plate	800, 870, 940, 1010, 1080, 1150, 1220, 1290
	cranial plate	0, 70, 140, 210, 280, 350, 420
	SAIMD-U	30, 100, 170, 240, 310, 380, 450, 520, 590, 660, 730, 800
YoonSun	shoulder	-70, 0, 70, 140, 210, 280, 350, 420, 490, 560, 630, 700, 770, 840
	ankle plate	600, 670, 740, 810, 880, 950, 1020, 1090
	cranial plate	0, 70, 140, 210, 280, 350, 420

5.1 Passive Implants

Simulations have been done using Sim4Life V7.2. The field inside birdcage coil HP_B60_L70 has been simulated for channels I and Q at 64 and 128 MHz. Those simulations have been used as input for Huygens source around the human models from the ViP with implants implanted using virtual surgery and/or placement of the implant at the accurate position and setting accurate voxeling priorities where the implant is prioritized over the body. To achieve circular polarization, the input field of the I channel of the birdcage coil has to be delayed by 0.25 periods so that the Q channel is shifted 90° ahead. For YoonSun, additional corner sources are set up to cancel the effects caused by the source boxes overlapping with the model of the coil. The fields from within these corner sources is shifted by 180° ahead, which is equivalent to a delay of 0.5 periods. This leads to a total necessary delay of 0.75 periods for the I channel corner sources and 0.5 periods for the Q channel corner sources. This is the same approach as used for MRiXViPV2.2. Simulations have been done with a base grid of 2mm resolution with a box of 1 mm resolution in the area around the implant (bounding box enlarged by 10 mm on each side). Only for the cranial plate, a resolution of 0.5 mm in the area surrounding the plate has been used.

The placement of the ankle plate was done in a previous task so that the ankle plate was positioned as close as possible on the bone, but did not reach into the bone / overlap with the bone. This led to the ankle plate sticking outside of the body at some places because the fat, muscle and skin tissue was not thick enough over the bone to encompass the whole plate. At these locations, a layer was created over the ankle plate and the material properties of skin were assigned to this layer so that the metal of the plate would not be directly in contact with air. The voxeling priority of the layer was set to be lower than the voxeling priorities of the ankle plate and the tissues of the body.

Additionally to the simulations with the implants, simulations for each channel (I and Q) have been performed for the human models in the HP_B60_L70 birdcage coil at the determined

positions without any implants. From these, a scaling factor has been determined for each position so that the average B1+ field magnitude in the slice at the isocenter of the coil (only considering the human tissue voxels, excluding the background) is 1 μ T (using the IMAnalytics tool).

The fields from the simulations including the implants have then been resampled to achieve a resolution of 2mm everywhere and scaled using the previously determined scaling factors.

The results have been provided as input for the next activity as .mat files. Because the Matlab exporter only exports axes at the voxel edges, the axes were manually adapted to create the axes referring to the center of the voxels.

5.2 Active Implant

The SAIMD-U, as defined in Annex U of ISO 10974:IS1 (2021 draft), was taken as an example for a standard active implant. For incident RF fields, the hotspot is usually at the lead tip, which was simulated in homogenous body-average tissue simulating medium. The distribution around the lead tip was then placed at an appropriate position in the body of a human model. The individual power values for each position have been determined by performing a Tier3 analysis with the IMAnalytics tool, using the scaled SAIMD-U transfer function from Annex U and a generic pacemaker routing at B1+ operating mode, scaling B1+ to 1 μ T as described in the section about passive implants. As input, the simulations for the I and Q channels without any implant at each position were again used.

The simulations for the IPG of the SAIMD-U were performed as for the passive implants described above. The model used for the simulation consisted of the IPG metal can only. The hollow parts inside of the IPG have been assigned the properties of air (chamber in the center) or an insulator with relative permittivity 3 (round holes for connectors). The results from the IPG and lead will be combined in a future activity.

Results

Passive Implants

The electric loss density in a slightly enlarged bounding box around the human models with implants was simulated, extracted on a grid of 2mm in all directions, and scaled to 1 μ T average B1+ field magnitude in the slice at the isocenter of the coil.

Active Implant

The deposited power extracted around the tip of the SAIMD-U lead within the -30 dB contour was 6.161e-8 W at 64 MHz and 3.400e-8 at 128 MHz in the separate lead tip simulations. The target tip deposited power values (in W) for each position and frequency which were determined using IMAnalytics are listed in Table 3 and Figures 11 and 12.

Table 3: Target deposited powers at SAIMD-U lead tip (in W).

Position / Frequency	64 MHz	128 MHz
30	0.003413	0.006014
100	0.007563	0.009639
170	0.011134	0.012712
240	0.01513	0.023597
310	0.016356	0.032438
380	0.01643	0.03659
450	0.015529	0.030868
520	0.012891	0.019755
590	0.008001	0.009391
660	0.003252	0.003414
730	0.000808	0.000712
800	0.000237	3.78E-05
Position / Frequency	64 MHz	128 MHz
30	0.003413	0.006014
100	0.007563	0.009639
170	0.011134	0.012712
240	0.01513	0.023597
310	0.016356	0.032438
380	0.01643	0.03659
450	0.015529	0.030868
520	0.012891	0.019755
590	0.008001	0.009391
660	0.003252	0.003414
730	0.000808	0.000712
800	0.000237	3.78E-05

Figure 11: Target deposited powers at SAIMD-U lead tip at 64 MHz.

Figure 12: Target deposited powers at SAIMD-U lead tip at 128 MHz.

The distribution around the SAIMD-U lead tip has been extracted on a grid of 2mm in all directions and placed in a box with a grid corresponding to the grid used for the results for the passive implants so that the center of the distribution lies at the position of the lead tip of a generic pacemaker routing. The distribution has been scaled so that the deposited power extracted within the -30dB contour corresponds to the target powers shown in the above table.

Additionally, simulations with the SAIMD-U IPG only have been done in the same way as described above for the passive implants.

6 Activity A3.3.4

INRIM will perform in silico GC simulations for the exposure scenarios identified in A3.3.1, using the digital models developed in A3.3.2.

All GC simulations have been performed complying with the positions, implants and sequences selected in activity A3.3.1. Each simulations has been repeated twice to compare the effect of the reaction (skin effect) on the power deposition within each implant. Due to the negligible role played by tissues in GC heating, all the simulations have been performed in air in a spatially homogeneous magnetic field corresponding to that generated by the GCs in the relevant implant position.

Gradient simulations were performed in Sim4Life and with a home-made validated code³ when simulations involved the ASTM phantom and anatomical body models, respectively. A 2mm voxel resolution was seen to be sufficient to achieve numerically stable results, and

³ Arduino Alessandro, Bottauscio Oriano, Brühl Rüdiger, Chiampi Mario, Zilberti Luca. In silico evaluation of the thermal stress induced by MRI switched gradient fields in patients with metallic hip implant. *Physics in Medicine & Biology*, 2019, doi: 10.1088/1361-6560/ab5428

the simulation domain was restricted to the region of the metallic implants since the power deposited by the GCs in the phantom and body tissues is negligible.

In simulations involving the ASTM phantom, the implants were exposed to a harmonic, spatially homogeneous, magnetic field directed along the direction which maximizes the induced heating. An algorithm implemented in Sim4Life determined the worst exposure direction, and simulations were performed at 1750 Hz as suggested by the ISO 10974 draft IS1 standard. These simulations exposed the implants to an arbitrary power, as the temperature increases were scaled to a reference peak value at a later stage.

Simulations involving MR pulse sequences and realistic body models followed the structure discussed in Arduino et al.,³ and complied with the implementation described by Bottauscio et al.⁴ As a consequence of the frequency content of the gradient waveform harmonic spectrum in the considered MR sequences, electromagnetic (EM) simulations modeled the skin effect in order to achieve more reliable results.

7 Activity A3.3.5

Starting from the data collected in A3.3.3 and A3.3.4, INRIM will perform thermal simulations either comparing the results obtained with RF and GC acting separately or superposing their contributions.

Thermal simulations have been performed in three different scenarios:

1. Only power from RF
2. Only power from GC
3. Both RF and GC powers

Given a specific sequence, the RF power have been scaled to the average power associated to the $B_{1,i}^+$ required to obtain the flip angle α_i needed by the sequence. The $B_{1,i}^+$ refers to the spatial average within the slice at the isocenter of the coils and it is obtained as:

$$B_{1,i}^+ = \frac{\alpha_i}{\gamma \tau_i}$$

where γ is the gyromagnetic ratio and τ_i is the i-th pulse duration. The RF power P_{RF} associated to the considered scenario is therefore obtained as:

$$P_{RF} = P_{1\mu T} \frac{1}{TR} \sum_i \tau_i \left(\frac{B_{1,i}^+}{1 \mu T} \right)^2$$

where $P_{1\mu T}$ is the power associated to a B_1^+ of 1 μ T averaged on the isocenter slice and TR is the repetition time. Since the thermal regulation has not been accounted for in

⁴ Bottauscio Oriano, Chiampi Mario, Hand Jeff, Zilberti Luca. A GPU Computational Code for Eddy-Current Problems in Voxel-Based Anatomy. IEEE Transactions on Magnetics, 2015, doi: 10.1109/TMAG.2014.2363140

simulations, the RF temperature distributions associated to the same implant position and different sequences simply scales with the power value P_{RF} .

The power density distributions resulting from GC and RF simulations were extracted on a regular 2mm grid. During GC exposure, the tissues heat up indirectly, due to thermal diffusion from the metallic components of the implant, whereas during exposure to RF, the heat diffuses from the tissues to the implant, where the direct thermal effect of RF fields is negligible.

Pennes' bioheat equation was expressed in terms of temperature elevation with respect to the temperature at rest and solved, by means of a home-made code^{3,5}. In the case of the anatomical body models, the bioheat equation also modeled the blood perfusion in the tissues, according to the parameters reported in the database of the IT'IS Foundation. This led to two temperature increase distributions, one due to GC alone and another to RF alone. Finally, the temperature increase due to the simultaneous presence of gradient and RF effects was obtained as summation of the previous GC and RF temperature distributions. Thanks to the linearity of the Pennes' equation, this corresponded to solve the problem using the sum of the two power distributions as the forcing term.

The analysis with the ASTM phantom combined, point by point, the spatial distributions of the temperature increases produced by the GC and RF fields, scaled to the same peak value within the phantom.

Simulations involving the MR pulse sequences and realistic body models scaled the gradient power according to the running sequence waveform and the RF power according to the required flip angle, RF pulse duration and modulation envelope, i.e. a *sinc* function with 0.5 apodization coefficient.

Both powers were averaged over the repetition time (TR) of the sequence and used as a source of the thermal problem. The GC and RF temperature increases were combined in two ways: the first by summing GC and RF temperature increases scaled to the same maximum value across the landmarks, and the second by summing GC and RF temperature increases as obtained from the actual powers generated by the relevant MR pulse sequence.

All temperature increases are provided as peak values across the computation domain, for a 30 min exposure to the different power sources.

8 Activity A3.3.6

INRIM and ITIS will define correction factors to account for the effect of superposition of RF and GC heating to be considered for an extension of the ASTM F2182 Standard related to RF heating of passive devices.

⁵ Arduino Alessandro, Bottauscio Oriano, Chiampi Mario, Zilberti Luca. Douglas–Gunn Method Applied to Dosimetric Assessment in Magnetic Resonance Imaging. IEEE Transactions on Magnetism. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TMAG.2017.2658021

Table 4 collects the relative enhancements of the peak temperature increases in the ASTM phantom due to the simultaneous exposure to GC and RF fields, with respect to the peak temperature increase obtained with GC or RF alone scaled to the same reference value.

Relative enhancements range from 17-67% at 1.5T and from 24-51% at 3T, depending on the implant.

Table 4: Relative enhancements of the maximum temperature increase due to the simultaneous application of GC and RF fields with the anatomical body models, with respect to the temperature increase due to GC or RF alone. For each implant and MR pulse sequence, RF and GC temperature increases were scaled to the same maximum value across the landmarks.

Implant	Relative enhancement (%)	
	1.5 T	3 T
AnklePlate	17	28
CranialPlate	67	51
Hip	29	40
Knee	39	24
Shoulder	21	23

The exposure conditions of the implants inside the ASTM phantom are quite different from those in a clinical setup. This reflects on the temperature increase enhancements obtained when the analysis involved MR pulse sequences and realistic body models, and the GC and RF temperature increases were scaled to the same maximum values across all landmarks before being combined (Figure 13 and Figure 14) . In this regard, Table 5 collects the relative enhancements of the peak temperature increases in the cases of realistic MR pulse sequences (Table 6) and anatomical human body models.

The results show that the maximum relative enhancements never exceed 9% and 11% at 1.5T and 3T, respectively. It is interesting to notice that, most of the time, the maximum temperature increase due to the simultaneous exposure to GC and RF occurs at the same landmark as in the case of exposure to the GC field alone.

Figure 13: Peak temperature increase, in kelvin, on the six implants exposed to different MR pulse sequences as a function of multiple axial landmarks. Results refer to 1.5T exposure to the RF EM field alone (red line), GC EM field alone (green line) and simultaneous application of RF and GC EM fields (blue line). The gray area highlights the enhancement of the peak temperature increase due to the simultaneous exposure to RF and GC EM fields with respect to the maximum between the peak temperature increase due to RF or GC alone.

Figure 14: Peak temperature increase, in kelvin, on the six implants exposed to different MR pulse sequences as a function of multiple axial landmarks. Results refer to 3T exposure to the RF EM field alone (red line), GC EM field alone (green line) and simultaneous application of RF and GC EM fields (blue line). The gray area highlights the enhancement of the peak temperature increase due to the simultaneous exposure to RF and GC EM fields with respect to the maximum between the peak temperature increase due to RF or GC alone.

Table 5: Relative enhancements of the maximum temperature increase due to the simultaneous application of GC and RF fields with the anatomical body models, with respect to the temperature increase due to GC or RF alone. For each implant and MR pulse sequence, RF and GC temperature increases were scaled to the same maximum value across the landmarks.

Implant	Sequence	Relative enhancement (%)	
		1.5 T	3 T
AnklePlate	EPI-X	0.52	0.95
	EPI-Y	0.12	1.35
	EPI-Z	1.05	1.56
	FISP	0.52	0.95
CranialPlate	EPI-X	1.53	4.36
	EPI-Y	1.72	4.11
	EPI-Z	0.85	2.85
	FISP	0.91	3.37
Hip	EPI-X	2.53	2.47
	EPI-Y	4.24	4.00
	EPI-Z	3.06	3.11
	FISP	1.85	1.70
Knee	EPI-X	5.70	10.19
	EPI-Y	8.17	4.49
	EPI-Z	4.20	4.97
	FISP	4.20	4.97
SAIMD-U	EPI-X	5.97	7.62
	EPI-Y	5.97	7.62
	EPI-Z	3.30	4.55
	FISP	5.96	7.61
Shoulder	EPI-X	7.58	7.20
	EPI-Y	8.49	9.57
	EPI-Z	7.42	8.47
	FISP	6.92	6.82

Table 6: Main parameters of the sequences considered for the analysis. Maximum Whole-Body (WB) averaged SAR refers to the maximum including all implants and exposure landmarks for the specific sequence. The three dB/dt rms values reported for the EPI sequence refer to the X, Y and Z readout directions, respectively.

	EPI	True-FISP
Flip angle	90°	45°
RF pulse duration (ms)	1.6	1
Time-BW product	4	4
TE (ms)	21	3.2
TR (ms)	43	6.4
Readout BW (kHz)	150	126.3
Matrix dimension	64 × 64	256 × 256
FOV (mm ²)	182 × 182	120 × 180
$B_{1,rms}^+$ (μT)	1.25	2.05
Maximum WB SAR @ 1.5 T, 3 T (W kg ⁻¹)	0.24, 0.71	0.65, 1.91
Maximum Gradient Amplitude (mT m ⁻¹)	22.0	25.6
Maximum Gradient Slew-rate (T m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	167	200
dB/dt rms @ r = 20 cm (T s ⁻¹)	40.6, 40.6, 34.0	33.0

Figures 13 and 14 show the peak temperature increase for 1.5T and 3% scenarios, respectively, resulting from the exposure to the specific MR pulse sequences whose parameters complied with those listed in Table 6. The figures report the temperature increases as a function of the axial position of the implant barycenter with respect to the scanner isocenter. The selection of the reported results was performed on a case-by-case basis, according to the combination of implant and sequence leading to the highest enhancements of the temperature increase due to the simultaneous effect of RF and GC EM fields with respect to RF and GC alone. This choice did not necessarily lead to show the cases where the absolute maximum temperature was reached. Nevertheless, the maximum peak temperature increases also played a role in excluding those scenarios where the heating due to both RF and GC were less prominent. The gray areas in the figures highlight the enhancement of the peak temperature increase when the RF and GC EM fields are applied simultaneously with respect to the maximum between the peak temperature increase due to the application of RF or GC EM field alone. Scenarios with the greatest distance between the blue and the dashed lines represent those where the addition of the two effects has the largest effect on the combined temperature increase. In this regard, Table 7 collects the maximum peak temperature increase enhancements for each exposure scenario. The table reports the enhancements as the peak temperature increase following the combined application of GC and RF, reported next to the maximum between the peak temperature increase due to RF or GC alone.

Table 7: Maximum peak temperature enhancements, among all the landmarks for each specific scenario. Each table entry reports the temperature increase due to RF or GC alone (the highest of the two as reported in the brackets) on the left of the temperature increase due to the combined effect of RF and GC. The temperature enhancement is added in square brackets near the temperature increase values. All temperature increases are reported in kelvin. For each implant, the first row refers to results at 1.5T and the second row at 3T. When the temperature increase enhancement resulted to be negligible for all the landmarks, a hyphen is reported in the corresponding table entry. Results shown in Figures 13 and 14 are reported in bold.

	EPI-X	EPI-Y	EPI-Z	True-FISP
Shoulder	1.64 (GC) - 1.71 [0.07]	0.59 (GC) - 0.67 [0.08]	1.29 (GC) - 1.35 [0.06]	0.89 (RF) - 1.03 [0.14]
	1.67 (RF) - 2.00 [0.33]	0.44 (GC) - 0.53 [0.09]	1.28 (RF) - 1.39 [0.11]	0.75 (GC) - 0.97 [0.22]
Knee	0.38 (GC) - 0.42 [0.04]	0.15 (RF) - 0.22 [0.07]	0.41 (GC) - 0.45 [0.04]	0.43 (RF) - 0.52 [0.09]
	0.70 (RF) - 0.82 [0.12]	0.70 (RF) - 0.94 [0.24]	0.75 (GC) - 0.87 [0.12]	1.08 (RF) - 1.29 [0.21]
Hip	0.33 (GC) - 0.42 [0.09]	0.79 (GC) - 0.87 [0.08]	0.21 (RF) - 0.30 [0.09]	1.01 (GC) - 1.18 [0.17]
	1.01 (GC) - 1.25 [0.24]	1.49 (GC) - 1.73 [0.24]	1.23 (GC) - 1.47 [0.24]	0.68 (GC) - 1.03 [0.35]
AnklePlate	-	-	-	-
	-	-	-	0.96 (RF) - 0.97 [0.01]
CranialPlate	0.14 (GC) - 0.17 [0.03]	0.10 (GC) - 0.14 [0.04]	0.12 (GC) - 0.15 [0.03]	0.13 (GC) - 0.17 [0.04]
	0.08 (RF) - 0.11 [0.03]	0.27 (RF) - 0.28 [0.01]	0.41 (GC) - 0.50 [0.09]	0.73 (RF) - 0.75 [0.02]
SAIMDU	0.56 (GC) - 0.63 [0.07]	0.85 (GC) - 0.93 [0.08]	0.50 (GC) - 0.57 [0.07]	0.24 (RF) - 0.35 [0.11]
	0.90 (GC) - 1.07 [0.17]	0.85 (GC) - 1.03 [0.18]	0.50 (GC) - 0.62 [0.12]	-

The U.S. Food & Drug Administration (FDA) suggests to include, along with the MR Conditional labeling of a Medical Device, the maximum allowable gradient slew rate per axis, the maximum permitted Whole-Body (WB) averaged SAR and/or maximum permitted head averaged SAR and the maximum B1+ rms admissible value. Constraining the maximum gradient slew rate reduces excessive GC heating, whereas limiting the maximum SAR and/or B1+ is useful to limit RF heating. Therefore, the previous quantities are restricted on the basis of testing results and a safety threshold in terms of maximum acceptable temperature increase. Independently of the actual value of the temperature increase threshold, when GC and RF testing are performed separately, applying independent limits is appropriate as long as the two heating effects do not combine significantly. When this holds true, if an MRI scan is performed e.g., at the maximum B1+ value, the peak of the RF-induced temperature increase may be close to the established threshold, if the clinical exposure is close to worst-case. Of course, if at the same maximum B1+ value, the gradient also contributes significantly to the heating, the actual peak temperature increase may be higher than the safety threshold. As a consequence, if the interaction of RF and GC heating is not properly accounted for, maximum temperature increases could reach unexpected and unsafe values, exposing the patient to a potential hazard.

The analyzed implants were not labeled as MR conditional, therefore the above information was not available; nor is there any generally accepted published value of maximum acceptable temperature increase. For these reasons, the study abstracted from these inputs, first by scaling the peak temperature increases obtained from GC and RF exposure to the same reference value, and then by considering an exposure to the EM field generated by MR sequences complying with normal operating mode and hardware watchdog.

The first analysis with the ASTM phantom aimed at reproducing the standard tests used to assess heating of conductive devices due to RF and GC exposures. These tests are designed to limit RF and GC exposure levels on the basis of a defined maximum acceptable temperature increase. Independently of its actual value, it is reasonable to assume it is the same for RF and GC exposures, as it depends primarily on the sensitivity of the surrounding tissues. This is why the analysis combined GC and RF temperature increases after scaling them to the same peak reference value. Results indicate maximum temperature increase enhancements up to 67% and 51% at 1.5T and 3T, respectively.

The clinical applicability of phantom testing is limited in several respects. First, the RF testing exposure is quite different from that of a typical clinical scenario, where the electric field could be far from homogeneous. Second, the phantom's geometrical, electrical and thermal properties differ from those of the human tissues. Finally, the ISO 10974 standard for GC testing does not require to determine the worst exposure direction on top of a previously calculated RF temperature increase. Therefore, there may be magnetic field directions leading to higher combined temperature increases, while causing lower temperature increases when the exposure is limited to GC alone. Thus, the phantom relative enhancements may under- or over-estimate those reasonably obtainable in clinical conditions. For this reason, the analysis shifted to simulations of implants inside realistic body models, exposed to the EM field generated by actual MR pulse sequences. The MR sequences were selected for their common application in clinical protocols and comparable exposure to RF and GC sources in terms of peak temperature increase.

For all landmarks, the first analysis scaled the temperature increases resulting from the independent exposure to GC and RF to the same maximum reference value. This represents the scenario where the implants have been independently tested for GC and RF induced heating and maximum exposure parameters, such as dB/dt rms and B1+ms, have been defined according to a maximum allowed temperature increase. Scaling the GC and RF temperature increases to the same maximum reference value across the landmarks emulates the scenario where the scan is limited by the implant's MR Conditional performance limits, rather than being allowed to follow a typical clinical sequence. This led to a decrease of the maximum relative temperature increase enhancements to 8.5% and slightly above 10% at 1.5T and 3T, respectively, with respect to those obtained with phantom.

While this analysis is useful to investigate the temperature increase enhancements due to the combined GC and RF effects when both are at their safety limits, it also reflects a clinically unrealistic scenario where the GC and RF waveform are designed to both reach the same maximum temperature increase. For this reason, the temperature increase due to GC and RF fields generated by realistic MR sequence parameters was also simulated. The sequence parameters were adopted from common scanning routines and complied with actual values of the gradient hardware watchdog limits. Whereas no information was available on the maximum safe B1+ rms for the considered unlabeled implants, the selected parameters complied with a scanner in Normal Operating Mode, namely with WB SAR equal or less than 2 W/kg. In particular, the maximum WB SAR amounted to 1.9 W/kg in the case of the hip and SAIMD-U implants positioned at 0.29m and 0.15m from the isocenter, respectively. In both cases, the 1.9 W/kg WB SAR value was obtained with the True-FISP

sequence at 3T. It is worth specifying that the WB SAR does not represent a sufficient safety metric in presence of metallic implants, where the "antenna effect" should also be considered. However, in absence of any other information, the simulated value at least ensured that the sequences complied with safety limits in absence of metallic implants. The gray areas in Figures 13 and 14 confirm that the temperature enhancement, due to the combined effect of GC and RF with respect to the maximum between GC or RF alone, depends on the specific scenario, i.e., implant, sequence and landmark. This comes as no surprise, since the shape of the object influences the GC and RF temperature increase distributions in a different way. In addition, the GC temperature increase distribution is also influenced by the direction of the gradient magnetic field, whose time evolution depends on both the landmark and the MR pulse sequence.

Furthermore, Figures 13 and 14 show that, for different implant positions, the maximum temperature increases due to GC and RF exposure alone are generally comparable. The ankle plate represents an exception since, as a result of its small cross-sectional area orthogonal to the GC magnetic field Z-direction, the heating due to GC is negligible.

The highest temperature enhancements, as reported in square brackets in Table 7, show a maximum of 0.35K in the case of the hip implant at 3T with the True-FISP sequence. This scenario also corresponds to the highest relative temperature enhancement, which amounts to 53%. Table 7, as well as Figures 13 and 14, show that the maximum enhancement can happen when either the GC or the RF peak temperature increase is dominant.

Table 7 reports the temperature increase in absolute terms, instead of relative ones as in the previous analysis.

It is worth studying the absolute temperature increase because of the linearity of the considered bioheat equation, which implies that the computed temperature increase distribution due to the combined effect of GC and RF equals the sum of the temperature increase distributions due to GC and RF alone.

When the EM field with the most severe thermal effect leads to a temperature increase sufficiently larger than the other, the spatial point where the temperature increase reaches its peak value will be the same for both the most severe and the combined cases.

As a consequence, when the power related to the most severe effect increases, while the other remains constant, the absolute temperature enhancement in the combined case does not change.

This condition occurs for all the scenarios collected in Table 7. In this perspective, the highest enhancements equal 0.33K when RF is the most severe effect and 0.35K when the most severe effect is GC. The first condition happens with the shoulder implant scanned with an EPI-X sequence and the second with the hip implant scanned with a True-FISP sequence.

All the temperature increase results are reported after 30 min of exposure. This duration equals that suggested by the ISO 10974 Standard and corresponds to a conservative estimation of the typical scan duration. Preliminary investigations also showed that the temperature increase due to GC exposure is almost at steady state after 30 min.

The generality of the results presented are limited by the adoption of only one human model per implant. This limitation comes from the fact that the accurate implant positioning procedure adopted required to find a proper matching between the available implant and body models. The implant and body models available in the authors' database did not allow for a large number of degrees of freedom, especially considering that the body posture cannot be sensibly changed if the body model had to fit inside the available RF coil and GC set. Furthermore, the implant positioning procedure revealed to be rather delicate requiring, in several occasions, the assistance of a specialized orthopedic surgeon. For these reasons, the analysis mainly focused on the Glenn body model, representative of an elderly male and, as such, with an increased probability of bearing an implant.

Another limitation of this work lies in the adoption of only one GC set and RF coil. Whereas multiple birdcage body coil models were available, only one GC model was available. In order to fit the RF body coil inside the 67cm internal diameter GC, an RF coil with a 60cm diameter had to be selected.

9 Summary of A3.3

In summary, results show that relative enhancements of the peak temperature increase of more than 65% can be found in phantom measurements when GC and RF are combined. Maximum relative enhancements of the temperature increase of about 10% are obtained with the implants in the anatomical body models when scaled to the same MR Conditional implant-based performance limits. Finally, realistic EPI and TrueFISP sequence parameters led to maximum absolute temperature increase enhancements above 0.3K and relative enhancements above 50%.

The outcomes prove to be useful for defining safety margins on the maximum allowable temperature increase, upon which the average $B1+rms$ and dB/dt rms are limited by the regulatory body in the MR conditional label of the medical devices. RF and GC heating test equipment, as well as test protocols for implant heating assessments, are different and independently developed. Building upon the provided results to account for the combined RF and GC effect in the definition of temperature safety margins would be a more practical solution than combining RF and GC in implant heating tests. Whereas this seems to be the most reasonable solution, the analysis may still be too limited in the number of simulated exposure scenarios. Reliable maximum temperature safety margins require extending the analysis to more implants, human body models and MR pulse sequences.

10 Activity A3.4.1

ITIS will perform ISO 10974 RF Tier 2, “Tier 2+”, and Tier 4 simulations on a set of generic implants with different parameters in order to define a conservative approach to predicting RF heating with minimal overestimation.

ASTM F2182-19^{ε2} and ISO 10974 require scaling the heating propensities of implants to *in vivo* incident (E-)fields during MR examination. The goal of this activity is to find a conservative, but not significantly overestimating, metric for incident E-fields to short implants which can be placed at many possible locations/orientations.

The ISO 10974 Tier 2 approach computes the 95th percentile of $|E_{tot}|$ over 10 g of tissue $\approx (2 \text{ cm})^3$; this neglects the averaging effect of the size of the implant, thus significantly overestimating the exposure. The Tier 3 approach for leaded implants uses a transfer function and complex-valued E_{tan} along well-defined clinical pathways; a “Tier 2+” option, $|E_{tan}|$ averaged along the device length as represented by bundles of splines, was published by Gas and Miaskowski (2019) and shown in ISMRM 2021 by Murbach, Doering, Schaefer, but also requires well-defined clinical placement. Tier 4 cannot capture all exposure scenarios, nor flexible placements.

In this activity the Gas & Miaskowski approach is extended with novel spline placement:

- 1) origin points are distributed along the surface or volume of a region of choice, and splines of length corresponding to the longest axis of the implant are cast outward in each direction;
- 2) $|E_{tan}|$ averaged along each spline is assessed, and the 95th percentile value over all exposure scenarios extracted with IMAanalytics (ZMT) and MRlxViP to estimate the maximum E-field picked up by the implant.

Validation was performed for a 10 cm long plate-like implant which can be placed at many locations about the pelvis, and a shielded IPG/pump which can be placed anywhere in the abdominal fat layer, as follows:

- 1) estimate the incident E-fields with the new approach and with Tier 2;
- 2) perform coupled EM-FDTD and thermal simulations of implants exposed to an isoelectric incident field tangential to the maximum length in the suitable phantom; scale the results to the fields in step 1;
- 3) perform Tier 4 simulations in ViP models, and compare simplified metrics to Tier 4 results in terms of temperature rise enhancement.

Figure 15 shows the tangential E-field distribution along the generated spline bundles for a representative exposure.

Figure 15: Placement of validation cases. Top: 10cm plate-like implant along the pelvis, shown with a representative E-field distribution during MRI (left), and the corresponding 10cm splines extracted along the pelvis surface (right). Bottom: Placement region for implanted pump in the abdominal fat of ViP model Duke (left), and splines with length of the long implant long diagonal (right).

The reduction in overestimation of the 95th percentile incident E-field compared to Tier 2 was 9 dB for the abdominal implant, and 10 dB for the long implant in the pelvis, at both 64 and 128 MHz.

Based on the Tier 4 result at the worst-case, the effective scaling factor for iso-electric exposure was 2.4dB lower for the abdominal implant, and 3.2dB for the pelvis plate, compared to the proposed metric, at both 64 and 128 MHz.

Figure 16: Unscaled incident E-field distributions visualized along tangential incident fields throughout the pelvis and abdominal fat regions, for an abdominal imaging landmark in Duke at CP.

The novel metric complements the established metrics in ISO 10974 to quantify the range of possible incident E-fields that can realistically contribute to RF-heating. Tier 4 can be used to demonstrate its conservativeness.

The incident fields estimated by the proposed novel approach were significantly below the Tier 2 estimation while remaining conservative to Tier 4 for both the implanted pump and the plate-like passive implant with variable orientations.

While the conservativeness of Tier 4 is limited by the access of the CAD model to the site of the worst-case incident field, the proposed metric can achieve full coverage of the target surface or volume and generate the desired statistics using the same tools and effort as Tiers 2 / 3.

11 Activity A3.4.2

ITIS will perform validation SAR/temperature RF measurements on selected generic implants from A3.4.1 with defined conditions to assess the accuracy and conservativeness of the prediction approaches.

11.1 Validation and Confidence Interval of RF-Heating

The validation of the accuracy and conservativeness of the “Tier 2+” approach defined in A3.4.1 extends the confidence interval of the Tier 3 library and toolset, IMAanalytics with MRlxViP, from where the incident fields are derived. The confidence interval of the use of IMAanalytics with the MRlxViP library for a generic elongated implant, which was estimated by following the standard guidelines defined by the Guide to the Measurement of Uncertainty (GUM) and by the ASME V&V 10, is shown in Table 8. The procedure is based on describing the total uncertainty of the evaluation as the convolution of independent uncertainty sources using Type B evaluation. Each uncertainty term was evaluated in terms of its contribution to variation of the final result (power deposition at a hotspot or induced voltage at lead terminal).

Therefore, the uncertainty contribution of each term comprises both the intrinsic variation of the source of uncertainty, and the local sensitivity of the final result to that variation – thus the uncertainties are presented as unitless factors, in decibels (as they are applicable for deposited power and for voltage).

The uncertainty associated with other IMAanalytics inputs, such as uncertainty of the transfer function models or routings/regions of interest, must be assessed separately and included in the final confidence interval.

Table 8: Confidence interval of IMAnalytics + MRlXViP output (deposited power or induced voltage) due to uncertainty of in vivo exposure conditions.

Description	Specific Uncertainty (dB)	Probability distribution	Divisor	Standard uncertainty (dB)
Numerical modeling	0.2	N	1	0.2
The uncertainty of the simulation to generate the exposure data of MRlXViP attributed to grid resolution, simulation time, and absorbing boundary conditions was evaluated for the ViP phantom Duke.				
Anatomy	-	-	-	-
The uncertainty attributed to anatomical variation of patients can be large and is very difficult to assess. While the MRlXViP dataset comprises twelve patients in numerous scan conditions which aim to cover the patient population, typically the worst-case exposure condition observed is used to determine safety.				
RF-coil	-	-	-	-
In order to capture the uncertainty due to the physical variation of the RF-coils, we consider 10 RF birdcage resonators with dimensions concluded from the survey summarized above. Exposures from all 10 resonators are used, and the highest induced power deposition or terminal voltage condition is used to determine safety.				
Clinical routing / region of interest	0.15	R	$\sqrt{3}$	0.09
The power deposition was evaluated for six different generic implant routing groups defined in [10]. The number of clinical routings per group vary from 1, 5, 10, and 100 routings. The uncertainty was taken to be the maximum difference in the power deposition obtained from the different number of routings per group.				
ViP model and tissue parameters	1.37	R	$\sqrt{3}$	0.79
To date, we are able to establish only the upper bound of the uncertainty associated with the anatomical fidelity of the models (e.g., tissue segmentation, tissue composition, and tissue parameters). The power deposition of a generic implant (insulated wire of 40 cm in length) was evaluated for five ViP phantoms (Fats, Duke, Ella, Billie, and Thelonious) with the nominal dielectric properties of tissue follow that published in the IT'IS tissue database. The same procedure was repeated for the five ViP phantoms assuming homogeneous dielectric properties of tissue taken from the body average of each phantom.				
Patient position	0.5	N	1	0.5
The power deposition was evaluated for the ViP phantom Duke at the $z = 70$ cm imaging position. The phantom is translated in the transverse plane by 10 cm from the nominal position; two positions in the anterior-posterior direction and two positions in the medial-lateral direction.				
B1 exposure limit	0.1	R	$\sqrt{3}$	0.06
The numerical simulations of RF exposure were obtained from Huygens' boxes (equivalence theorem) where the birdcage coil is replaced by an equivalent boundary condition over a Gaussian surface surrounding the ViP phantoms. The evaluation was conducted at the normal-mode exposure limit, where exposure is limited by wbSAR, hSAR, or pbSAR. The uncertainty budget of the exposure limit is determined from the maximum difference, between the wbSAR obtained with and without Huygens' box, of the five ViP phantoms.				
Combined Std. Uncertainty (RSS, k=1)				0.96 dB
Expanded 95% Confidence Interval (RSS, k=2)				1.92 dB

The confidence interval of ISO 10974 Tier 3 evaluations of deposited power around SAR hotspots in tissue, or induced voltage in a channel, was assessed for tests performed by the IT'IS Foundation on AIMD in previous EMPIR project (MIMAS 17IND01). In that report, the calculation of temperature rise, thermal dose, and tissue damage corresponding to the assessed *in vivo* deposited power were not discussed as being outside the scope of the ISO 10974 approach. Unlike deposited power, the local temperature rise depends strongly on the shape of the lead tip as well as the tissue environment around the hotspot (tissue properties and distribution).

In this work, the MIMAS report was extended to cover *in vitro* temperature rise uncertainty around strong gradients such as found near screw tips or AIMD electrodes.

To appropriately measure the temperature rise, a system check has to be conducted to guarantee proper functionality of the equipment. If possible, the racetrack in the vicinity of the electrode should be cut away to minimize its contribution to the measurement. The system check consists of the following steps:

- measure the electrical and thermal properties of the TSM together with the corresponding temperature;
- verify the correct operation of the measurement system,

by conducting a background temperature rise measurement and comparing it to the expected value from the measured E-field. In order to minimize errors from disturbing the test item and slurry, the system check is performed with the test item in place. The background temperature rise measurement location should be selected to have the least enhancement due to the implant (<-30dB) and be at least 2cm away from any interface.

1. Fill up the desired phantom with fresh TSM in slurry form. TSM should not contain air bubbles.
2. Measure the electrical and thermal conductivity of the TSM using a thermometer, the DAK, and the thermal conductivity meter. All values should be close to nominal, i.e. within the range defined by the uncertainty budget for your test protocol.
3. Let the covered phantom rest (e.g. over-night) to equilibrate and for air bubbles to dissolve.
4. Before starting the measurement, check that TSM properties have not drifted.
5. Mount the phantom in the exposure system, and configure it to expose the test item to a uniform incident E-field
7. Validate the incident B-field as appropriate.
9. Mount the temperature probe and position it at the defined location for background temperature rise measurement.
10. Record the baseline temperature; temperature drift should be ≥ 10 dB below the measured temperature rise of the sample.

12. Engage the exposure. The measurement protocol should record a temperature rise of at least $5 \times$ sensor resolution; the total temperature rise should be $<3K$ to avoid change of the TSM properties.

13. Mount the SAR probe and measure the total E-field at the same location as the temperature, rotating the probe 360° and averaging total E.

14. The measured ΔT has to be equal to $\sigma E^2 / (\rho c) \times t_{\text{meas}}$ within the confidence interval defined in Table 9. If this is the case then the measurement system is validated.

15. Move to the first measurement point defined for the test item (e.g., dark blue in Figure 17). Repeat 10 - 12.

Repeat for the desired number of measurement points.

The background temperature rise should be validated against the analytical solution ($SAR = C \, dT/dt$). The SAIMD-1-200mm temperature rise can be validated against numerical simulations, as shown in Figures 18 and 19. Target values can also be obtained from Annex I of ISO 10974.

Figure 17: Schematic of SAIMD-1-200mm with the locations of interest (dark and light blue) for temperature measurement.

$d = 1.5 \text{ mm}$

Figure 18: Numerical benchmark for p1 and p2, normalized to background incident field. The background temperature rise has been removed from the temperature rise due to SAIMD-1-200mm. The numerical data has been averaged over the dimensions of the tip of the probe ($d = 0.88\text{mm}$).

A correction factor has to be applied to compensate for the physical size of the temperature probe and the temperature gradient in z-direction (gradient compensation section in Table 9). Figure 19 shows the correction factor, derived from a linear fit of SAIMD-1 measurements with two different models of temperature probe.

Table 9: Example confidence interval of temperature rise validation at the highest heating point (point 1, dark blue) of SAIMD-1-200mm. References marked with [?] are not generalized and should be updated as appropriate for the TSM selected.

Source of Uncertainty	Tolerance in dB	Prob. Distrib.	Div.	c_i	Std. Unc. in dB	Reference or Comment
Incident Field						
MITS drift	0.1	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.06	MITS manual
SAR probe calibration in TSM	0.28	N	1	1	0.28	EX3D cal. cert.
SAR probe modulation response	0.02	N	1	1	0.02	EX3D cal. cert.
SAR probe axial isotropy	0.07	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.04	EX3D cal. cert.
SAR probe hemispherical isotropy	0.3	R	$\sqrt{3}$	0	0	Field is perpendicular to probe
Readout electronics	0.04	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.02	DASY manual
Temperature Probe						
Temperature probe dT/dt	0.11	N	1	1	0.11	T1 cal. cert.
Probe positioning w.r.t. sample	0.44	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.26	0.2 mm applied to axial gradient
Volume averaging	0.09	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.03	max deviation due to different averaging
Media Properties						
Electrical conductivity (deviation from nominal)	0.03	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.02	0.6% deviation
Permittivity (deviation from nominal)	0.05	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.03	2.7% deviation
Electrical conductivity (temperature dependency)	0.03	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.02	0.5% variation over 0.3 K
Permittivity (temperature dependency)	0.00	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.00	0.1% variation over 0.3 K
Thermal conductivity	0.14	N	1	1	0.14	[?]
Heat capacity (x)	0.03	N	1	1	0.03	[?]
Density (y)	0.07	N	1	1	0.07	[?]
Combined Measurement Uncertainty					0.44	
Simulation						
E grid resolution	0.25	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.14	Sensitivity analysis with 2x resolution
Thermal boundary	0.02	N	1	1	0.02	[?]
Temp. grid resolution	0.25	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.14	Sensitivity analysis with 2x resolution
Simulation convergence	0.1	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.06	Sensitivity analysis with 2x sim. length
Combined Simulation Uncertainty					0.21	
Gradient Compensation						
Gradient calc.	0.85	R	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.50	gradient analysis over 2,3,5 mm
Linear fit	1.2	N	1	1	1.20	95% confidence bounds
Combined Gradient Compensation Uncertainty					1.30	
Combined Std. Uncertainty (k = 1)					1.39	

11.2 Validation and Confidence Interval of GC Heating

In this activity, the work was extended to include this uncertainty for *in vitro* RF and GC exposures. The measurements were conducted on a semi-rigid titanium (ASTM F67) cranial mesh manufactured by Medartis AG (Basel, Switzerland). The implant was 93 mm×93 mm and its thickness was 0.6 mm. The thickness of the implant corresponds to the diameter of its one-dimensional structure, so that $r= 0.3$ mm. It was equipped with three optical fibre temperature probes, two positioned in the peripheral regions, where the largest temperature increase was expected to be induced, and one in the central region, as shown in Figure 20. The probes were connected to an eight-channel AccuSens signal conditioner produced by Opsens (Québec, Canada) sampling at 20 Hz. The manufacturer declared an overall accuracy of ± 0.30 °C and a resolution of 0.01 °C.

Experiment

Model

Figure 20: Experimental setup and virtual modelling. (a) Semi-rigid cranial mesh in titanium equipped with the optical fibre temperature probes. (b) System of GCs for cylindrical MRI scanners. (c) Phantom filled with expanded polystyrene grains. (d) Computational model of the cranial mesh with depicted the boxes of the active parts of the temperature probes. (e) Computational domain including the phantom with the cranial mesh and the model of the GCs.

In a first experiment, simulating the heat transfer from the cranial mesh towards soft tissues, the implant with the positioned probes were plunged into a cuboid container (base of 13 cm × 44 cm, height of 20 cm) filled with gel simulating average tissue parameters produced by Zurich MedTech AG (Zurich, Switzerland) in accordance with ISO/TS 10974. In a second experiment, simulating an almost adiabatic condition, the same cuboid container was filled with expanded polystyrene grains whose diameter varies between 1 mm and 3 mm. The base of the implant was fixed in a slot cut in a spongy support to keep it in the correct position within the container. In particular, the implant was positioned at 45° with respect to the container walls to have it perpendicular to the generated magnetic field, which is the configuration expected to maximize the induced temperature increase.

The magnetic field was generated by the system of actively shielded GCs with whole-body access for cylindrical MRI scanners. Precisely, it is the model Solaris-R manufactured by Nanjing Cichen Medical Technology Co., Ltd (Nanjing, China). The system, featuring three coils to generate gradient magnetic fields along three orthogonal directions, has an internal diameter of about 67 cm and a total length of about 150 cm. The gradient directions determine the used reference system, with \hat{z} directed longitudinally with respect to the coils, \hat{y} directed vertically and \hat{x} perpendicular to the other two directions.

The GCs were supplied by a NG500 1.3 gradient amplifier built by Prodrive Technologies (Eindhoven, The Netherlands) able to drive each coil independently and to provide a peak current of 1000 A and a maximum voltage of 940 V. To dissipate the loss power in the coil conductors due to the high current values, a water cooling system was connected to the coils. The cooling system made negligible the impact of the heating dissipated by the GCs' conductors on the temperature values measured on the implant, as verified through a fourth optical fibre temperature probe positioned at the boundary of the phantom, where no heating due to the currents induced on the cranial mesh was expected. In the experiment, the coils generating gradients directed along \hat{x} and \hat{z} were driven with two in-phase sinusoidal currents at the frequency of 2 kHz. According to the numerical model described in Section 2.2.2, the peak current intensities of 150 A were such that a peak magnetic field of 3.5 mT was generated at the implant barycentre, located at $x = 14$ cm, $y = 0$ and $z = 30$ cm with respect to the coil isocentre (i.e., the central point where all the coils generate a null magnetic field). The temperature detected by the optical fibre temperature probes were recorded every 2 s for 900 s of continuous exposure of the cranial mesh to the harmonic magnetic field generated by the GCs. Temperature recording started 30 s before switching on the power amplifier to acquire the value at which the system and the probes were thermalized.

Since the actual measurand to be compared with the simulation results is the temperature increase, an offset equal to the average of the temperature values recorded in the preliminary 30 s were applied to the measurement results.

The measurements were repeated two times a day apart without moving neither the probe nor the phantom, to assess the repeatability of the experiment.

Figure 21 depicts the measurement pipeline. The temperature probes attached to the implant were connected to the temperature acquisition.

Figure 21: Experiment pipeline. The experiment was monitored by a controller PC that collected the acquired temperature data through a serial connection with the temperature acquisition system. The same controller PC controlled the gradient amplifier through a LAN connection and monitored the generated currents through a Thunderbolt connection and an acquisition board connected through coaxial cables to the gradient amplifier. The gradient amplifier supplied the GCs through high current cables and the cranial mesh was exposed to the generated magnetic field.

Figure 22: Comparison between measurements and simulations. The noisy pale orange and pale red lines report the measurement results in the first and second repetition, respectively. The solid green and blue lines report the simulated results with the thermal seed model (purely 3D FEM) and the 3D–1D coupling,

respectively. The results are reported for the three channels illustrated in Fig. 18d for both the gel phantom and the polystyrene.

Figure 23. Temperature increase induced by MRI GCs on the cranial mesh immersed in gel (left) and polystyrene (right). (a) Result of the proposed approach based on 3D–1D coupling. (b) Result of the approximated thermal seed model (purely 3D FEM). (c) Difference between the results of the two models. In all the panels, horizontal and vertical axes are expressed in centimetres and the white rectangles represent the projections of the probes on the plane of the implant.

According to Figure 22, in the case of the gel phantom, both the approximated model based on thermal seeds and the complete 3D-1D coupled model agree with the noisy

measurement results. The numerical model and the computational procedure handling the 3D–1D coupling are, therefore, experimentally validated, as well as the thermal seed approximation. Interestingly, the 3D–1D coupled model evaluates a temperature increase detected by the thermal probes in the peripheral region (channels 1 and 2) that, after 900 s of exposure, is about 7% lower than the temperature increase estimated by the thermal seed model. At the same time, the temperature increase detected by the thermal probe near the centre of the implant (channel 3) according to the 3D–1D coupled model is slightly larger than that estimated by the thermal seed model. This happens because of the proper modelling of the thermal conductivity within the cranial mesh, along its thin but highly conductive branches.

Indeed, the dissipated power is mostly located near the edges at the boundary of the implant. Therefore, only part of the generated heat is transferred to the surrounding gel; the remaining part of the heat stays within the implant and moves towards the inner and corner regions, where no power is directly dissipated by the induced electrical currents.

This secondary physical effect, that tends to uniform the temperature in the implant by reducing its value in the hot-spots and increasing it elsewhere, cannot be described by the approach based on thermal seeds, whereas it is modelled by the 3D–1D approach, as highlighted in the map of the difference between the two estimated distributions in Fig. 23c.

The second experiment, with the cranial mesh plunged into the expanded polystyrene grains, led to a larger temperature increase and a clearer separation between the results obtained from the two models in channels 1 and 2. From the results reported in Fig. 22, the greater accuracy of the 3D–1D coupling approach with respect to the thermal seed model in describing the actual physical phenomenon is clear. After 900 s of exposure, the temperature increase computed with the 3D-1D coupled model is about 25% lower than the temperature increase estimated with the thermal seed model in both the peripheral probes (channels 1 and 2). Moreover, the trend of the temperature increase computed with the 3D–1D coupled model is in close agreement with the measurement results, especially during the first 100 s of the experiment.

Many reasons can motivate the separation between the two trends after this time period, like the imperfect modelling of the probe active part, as well as the thermal exchange with the environment through the boundary of the computational domain, and the not perfectly known thermal properties of the expanded polystyrene grains. Nonetheless, the reached agreement between experimental measurements and simulations of the proposed 3D–1D coupled model is satisfactory and proves its larger accuracy (i.e., its capability to better reproduce the experimental behaviour) with respect to the thermal seed model.

The discrepancy between measurements and simulations is also found in the results collected by the probe located in the centre of the implant (channel 3), where both the numerical models overestimated the measured values, although the agreement is larger than for the other probes. Although for this probe the two simulations lead to very similar results, making impossible to discriminate between them in terms of accuracy with respect to the measured trend, it is worth noting that the 3D–1D coupled model estimated a temperature increase about 5% larger than the thermal seed model. This happens because

of the heat transfer through the highly conductive metal of the implant, that is properly modelled by the 3D–1D coupling.

This fact becomes clearer by looking at the difference between the two temperature distributions estimated with the proposed method and the thermal seed approximation in Figure 23c. The difference is significantly larger than in the case of the gel phantom because the temperature increase computed with the 3D–1D approach is quite homogeneous within the entire implant (Figure 23a), whereas the result of the thermal seed model is strongly heterogeneous, directly reflecting the distribution of the Joule losses due to the induced electrical currents (Figure 23b). Moreover, the map of the difference reported in Figure 23c shows that near the vertices of the implant the temperature increase estimated using the 3D–1D approach is significantly larger than the values estimated with the thermal seeds. Precisely, near the vertices the thermal seed approximation underestimates the temperature increase of about 1.3 °C with respect to the 3D–1D coupled model, with a relative discrepancy of almost 35%.

12 Activities A3.4.3 and A3.4.4, and Conclusions

By comparing in silico simulations with phantom analysis, INRIM will evaluate the possibility to define optimal phantom thermal properties to reproduce in vitro the in-silico results and define hints to translate these results in vivo.

Based on the new procedure developed in Task 3.2, INRIM will study the possibility to combine GC heating tests performed on single implant components to get the final behaviour of the entire implant under realistic exposure scenarios.

The results of the previous activities are summarized in these last two activities. Tables 10 and 11 show the variation in maximum gradient-induced heating of two of the implant families studied, for the anatomy and exposure (high gradient field) studied. Notably, the behaviour of single implant components is different from that of the assembled implant, both with respect to the maximum peak temperature increase and anisotropy coefficients. Two strategies are applied to condense the results obtained with the single implant components. The first is by taking the maximum of the anisotropy coefficients computed for each component. The second is by scaling the anisotropy coefficients according to the ratio between the component peak temperature increase and the peak temperature increase of all the components composing the entire implant. The different behaviour is implant dependent; thus, exploiting simulations in implant testing makes this analysis less relevant.

The metrics derived in A3.4.1 can be used to assess the worst-case RF-heating with minimal overestimation; while the superposition of RF+GC heating can be estimated from the results in A3.3, or better, explicitly calculated by the methods derived there. The confidence interval of both RF (now including thermal gradient) and GC assessments has been estimated by comparison to validation measurements for each case, respectively.

Table 10: Maximum combined GC temperature rise enhancement of the studied knee implant family under maximum gradient heating conditions for the studied anatomical cases, with confidence interval statistics.

Implant Configuration	Max dT	RMSE(η)	max($\Delta(\eta)$)	min($\Delta(\eta)$)
Knee Complete	6.43 °C	-	-	-
Knee Tibial	5.81 °C	0.120	0.381	-0.020
Knee Tibial + Liner	6.16 °C	0.120	0.385	-0.015
Knee Femur	5.22 °C	0.083	0.199	-0.080
Knee Femur + Liner	5.52 °C	0.081	0.198	-0.064
Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.024	0.036	-0.064
Maximum Weighted Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.029	0.092	-0.064
MAX	6.43 °C			

Table 11: Maximum combined GC temperature rise enhancement of the studied hip implant family under maximum gradient heating conditions for the studied anatomical cases, with confidence interval statistics.

Implant Configuration	Max dT	RMSE(η)	max($\Delta(\eta)$)	min($\Delta(\eta)$)
Hip Complete	6.63 °C	-	-	-
Hip Acetabular Cup	4.85 °C	0.115	0.274	-0.025
Hip Acetabular Cup + Liner	5.03 °C	0.115	0.271	-0.024
Hip Stem & ball	3.58 °C	0.108	0.002	-0.172
Hip Stem & ball + Liner	3.99 °C	0.108	0.003	-0.169
Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.108	0.003	-0.169
Maximum Weighted Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.093	0.078	-0.169
MAX	6.63 °C			

With the conclusion of this STASIS deliverable report, and its associated publications and open-access tools, the goal has been achieved:

- gradient-induced heating concepts and procedures proposed in ISO/TS 10974 are extended to passive orthopaedic implants and fixation devices;
- a Tier 2+ approach is developed to reduce the overestimation of the safety limits in case of anisotropic implants, and to define testing procedures more relevant to the actual clinical conditions at which such implants are scanned;

- roles of gradient and RF as implant heating sources are investigated *in silico*; recommendations for combining results of RF and gradient testing are provided in view of standardised procedures;
- robust methodology to streamline the *in vitro* evaluation of bulky passive implants and translate into actual clinical MRI exposures with suitable confidence levels.

These results support and enable Deliverable 7, the work item to propose “Standard Test Method for Measurement of Gradient Magnetic Field Induced Heating On or Near Non-active Implants During Magnetic Resonance Imaging” as a draft ASTM test standard.